

DV-2025 Submission Confirmation: Entry Received

Success!

Your entry for the 2025 Diversity Visa program was received on Monday, October 30, 2023 at 2:02:11 AM EDT. Please do **NOT** close this window until you have printed this confirmation page or made a record of your Confirmation Number.

Entrant Name:

YUSUPOV, MURODJON

Confirmation Number:

20259GT5H9JNKODE

Year of Birth:

1997

Digital Signature:

07185B4104A92434005021F55ACA9FFF0D933166

Thank you for your entry for the 2025 Diversity Visa Program.

Please either print this page or make a record of the confirmation number before closing this window. You will not be able to retrieve this number after you close this window.

You must retain your confirmation number in order to check your entry status via [Entrant Status Check](#) between May 4, 2024 and September 30, 2025 to determine whether your entry was selected for further processing in the 2025 Diversity Visa Program. You will be **REQUIRED** to enter your confirmation number in combination with other personal information in order to check on your entry status.

Selectees will not receive selectee notifications or letters by regular postal mail from the Kentucky Consular Center (KCC).

Do not submit additional Entry Forms with this person as the Primary Entrant! Multiple entries will disqualify the Entrant from participation in the 2025 Diversity Visa Program.